

Community- Based Ecotourism in Sillery Gaon, West Bengal

Pallabi Rai* and Dr. Ishwarjit Singh Elangbam**

*M.A. Student and **Asst. Prof., Department of Geography, Sikkim University.

Received: Sep 15, 2025

Accepted: Oct 14, 2025

Published: Oct 15, 2025

Abstract

Community-Based Ecotourism (CBET) in Sillery Gaon, a picturesque Himalayan village in Kalimpong district of West Bengal, represents a model of sustainable rural tourism that harmonizes environmental conservation with socio-economic development. The paper has focus on community (both resident owners' of homestay and residents of non homestay) involvement in the management with external agents (who run homestay on lease), well being of staffs and tourist satisfaction and their perspectives in contributing local livelihood diversification, cultural preservation, and conservation of environment. There are 37 households in Sillery Gaon hamlet out of which 31 households have homestays in which 23 homestays leased out to external agents and 6 households do not have homestay but doing business and other activities which directly helps eco-tourism. There were 10 staffs mostly local and only three staffs came from out site and 15 domestic tourists who were found in homestays during survey were also surveyed. It was reported that leasing homestay reduce management responsibilities of the owners, better promotion and marketing and predictable regular income. Though, there is a grave concern about agents prioritize their profits, loss of local control, commodification erode gradually cultural heritage, authenticity and also affecting environment due to over crowding peak season from October to April and increasing waste.

Key Words: Authenticity, heritage, Agent, commercialization and environment

Introduction

Tourism has emerged as the fastest-growing industry. It contributes US\$10.9 trillion to global economy which is about 10% of global GDP and creating 357 million job (UNWTO, 2024). One form of tourism, i.e., ecotourism, is a nature-based travel practice, that has gained global attention in 21th centuries, for its potential to harmonize environmental conservation with socio-economic benefits. Ecotourism also creates awareness towards the conservation of natural and cultural assets both among the locals and

the tourists (Chakma et al., 2018). In rural areas, tourism often promotes infrastructural development, electrification, digital connectivity, and exposure to new income sources. However, several challenges include economic injustice, seasonal jobs, commoditization of culture, environmental degradation, etc. (Alamineh et al., 2023).

Community-based ecotourism (CBET) has gained prominence as a sustainable development strategy, particularly in rural India (Kumar, 2023). It emphasizes the active participation of local communities in tourism planning, management, and benefits from tourism activities. It is increasingly viewed as prominent effective livelihood strategy, offering economic opportunities for both men and women, particularly in rural and marginalized areas. It contributes to sustainable development by promoting community development, preserving cultural heritage, reducing poverty and inequality, and conserving natural environment (UNWTO, 2024).

CBET also seeks a balanced and harmonious development, considering compatibility with local economy components, cultural and environmental quality, and the diverse needs, interests, and potentials of the community and its inhabitants (Afua et al., 2022). A common expression of this model is homestay tourism, where local residents host tourists in their homes, thereby integrating tourism into daily life and local livelihoods (Chapagai et al., 2018).

Local women play an important role in the management of homestays. Homestays have become mechanism for community development, facilitating women's empowerment and challenging traditional gender roles (Acharya & Halpenny, 2013). CBET facilitates local entrepreneurship, supports environmental conservation through low-impact tourism, and integrates traditional culture such as local cuisine, festivals, and architecture into the visitor experience. In the context of Sillery Gaon, West Bengal, community-based ecotourism plays a significant role in addressing rural development by contributing alternative livelihoods in regions with limited traditional agriculture and employment. In remote and mountainous regions, where conventional development initiatives often fail, CBET has shown particular relevance. It can also support cultural preservation through the restoration of heritage sites and acts as a clean industry promoting the conservation of local resources (Ray et al., 2012).

Sillery Gaon nestled within the Paiengaon forest in the Kalimpong district of West Bengal has recently emerged tourist destination. Despite its natural beauty and cultural significance, including the Damsang Fort, the hamlet faces challenges such as homestay leasing, which

threatens cultural authenticity, leads to revenue leakage, strains local resources, and affects both environmental and economic sustainability. The paper focus on two aspects, identifying the stakeholders and their role in management of eco-tourism in the Sillery Gaon and second on socio-economic and environment implications of eco-tourism and perspectives of eco-tourist on eco tourism in the Sillery Gaon.

Study Area

Sillery Gaon is a small and beautiful hamlet located in the Kalimpong Sadar subdivision of West Bengal. The hamlet is located at 27°8'22.40"N latitude and 88°34'49.39"E longitude, at an elevation of about 1826.8 mts. Sillery Gaon is located approximately 23 km away from the Kalimpong town, and about 12 km away from Algarah (Figure no 1 and 2). Sillery Gaon is surrounded with the mixed tropical and pine forest, contributing to a unique ecological profile. It's rich biodiversity and scenic forest landscape attract sever visitors throughout the year, particularly nature lovers. The hamlet has a mesmerizing view of Mt. Kanchenjunga, the glimpse of meandering Teesta River, ruins of Damsang fort, Bhaley Dhunga, serene expansion of Silence Valley, and trekking route to Ramitey Dara view point and Ichye Gaon. The area experiences temperate climate, with an average summer temperature between 19°C to 27°C and falling temperature between 5°C to 17°C during winter. The hamlet receives an annual rainfall of about 2254 mm. According to Census 2011 data, Sillery Gaon has total population of 141 persons in 37 households, consisting of 77 males and 64 females, showing a balanced sex ratio. 22 people belong to Scheduled Castes and 22 belong to Scheduled Tribes. The population is ethnically diverse, primarily consisting of Tamang, Sherpa, Rai, Bhujel, Kami, and Damai community. The local cuisine is rooted in agrarian life. Cultural heritage is also maintained through household crafts created by the local craftsmen. In 2009, inspired from nearby areas four friends, Dilip Tamang, Kaji Tamang, Biru Tamang, and Kamal Tamang started the ecotourism with few family-run homestays in the area. At the time Sillery Gaon was a small hamlet with little infrastructure with no electricity supply and poor road connectivity. The narrow road connecting to the area was called as 'Ghore Road', (horse road) as horses used to travel from there (Maity, 2020).

Figure No. 1 Location Map of The Study Area

Source: Government of West Bengal, 2018

Figure no.2: Land use Land cover Map of Sillery Gaon

Source: Google Earth Imagery, <https://earth.google.com/web/> (extracted on 22/06/2025)

Result and Discussion

Data required for analysis has been obtained from both primary and secondary sources. The primary field survey was conducted by using semi-structured questionnaire to ensure the accuracy and depth of the findings. Data were collected from the entire households of the village, both homestay owners and non homestay to avoid sampling bias and to cover all relevant stakeholders. The total households of Sillery Gaon is 37 out of which 31 households engaged in homestay and 6 households did not engage homestay. In the survey included all 10 staffs who were working in homestays and included 15 tourist who were staying in the homestays during the survey. The survey was conducted in the month of January and February 2025.

Owners of Homestay

31 respondents of owners of the homestays belonged to age group 27-35 with 26% followed by 36-44 with 23%, suggesting that the young people in their late 20s to mid-40s are primarily operators of homestays. As they are largely associated with career building, entrepreneurial nature, and economic stability, making them more active in business operations. Their religious composition were Buddhist constitutes around 58%, 32% respondents belonged to Hindu are Gorkha and Christians represent only about 10%. The majority of the respondents attained only primary (52%) and secondary (42%) education levels, indicating that education is accessible at the basic level in the region. Their occupational structure were mainly drivers with 32% followed by homestay manager with 31%, 13% government service and full time farmer with 10%.

Table No.1: Number of rooms in homestays

Rooms	Total	Percentage
2-4 rooms	4	13
5-7 rooms	12	39
8-10 rooms	13	42
11 and more rooms	2	6
Total	31	100

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

Most homestays have around 5-10 rooms with 81%; hence, they tend to follow a mid-scale accommodation model. There are only 2 homestays (6%) with more than 11 rooms, indicating a preference for small compared to large commercial setups (Table no. 1). As these homestays are family-run businesses, limiting growth. The materials used for wall of homestay structure are timber and concrete blocks are equally preferred so that they seem to mix tradition and modernity. Timber is an expression of local architectural heritage that is heavily imported from the market due to its warm character in cold regions.

Table No. 2: Distribution of homestay owners by monthly income

Amount (in rupees)	Total	Percentage	Male (%)	Female (%)
Less than 10,000	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
10,000-20,000	19	61	11 (55)	8 (73)
20,000-30,000	9	29	6 (30)	3 (27)
30,000-40,000	3	10	3 (15)	0 (0)
More than 40,000	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Total	31	100	20 (100)	11 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

Sillery Gaon, situated in a rural location, does practice community-based ecotourism, which is very close to nature and allows the visitors to experience the rural livelihood, and does not support luxury or large-scale homestay operations. Out of 31 homestays 20 homestays owned by men and 11 owned by females. 61% of homestay owners, earn monthly earnings between Rs.10,000 to 20,000 per month, with a higher proportion of female owners (73%) as compared to men owners (55%) of home stay. This indicates that most homestays operate at a small or moderate scale, with limited pricing power and occupancy rates and the revenue may vary during tourist seasons. About 29% of respondents, earns monthly earnings ranging from Rs. 20,000 to 30,000 per month, with 30% of males and 27% of females. This is possible as these homestays have more rooms or additional services (local experiences, cuisine, tour guide, etc.), or the owners are also engaging in other services. Only 10% of male owners earn monthly between Rs. 30,000 to 40,000 per month who have more rooms (Table no 2).

Table No. 3: Main purpose of operating Homestay

Purpose	Total	Percentage	Male	Female
Income generation	29	94	19(95)	10 (91)
Cultural promotion	1	3	1 (5)	0 (0)
Tourism development	1	3	0 (0)	1 (9)
Total	31	100	20 (100)	11 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

The majority, with 94% of the homestay owners in Sillery Gaon, operate their homestays primarily to generate income as an extra income from other rural agriculture activities. While cultural heritage plays a significant role in the homestay experience, however, with only 3% who responded that cultural promotion similarly, only 3% for tourism development (Table no.3).

Table 4: Number of Leasing Homestays

Response	Total	Percentage	Male	Female
Yes, currently leasing	18	58	15 (75)	3(27.3)
Yes, have leased in the past	1	3	1 (5)	0 (0)
No, but considering	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Yes, half rooms of homestay are leased	5	16	1 (5)	4 (36.3)
No	7	23	3 (15)	4 (36.3)
Total	31	100	20 (100)	11 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

Out of 31 homestays 58% are being completely leased out to external agents, 16% homestays are leased half of their rooms to external agents and 3% had leased out but presently taken by owner. The remaining 23% of homestays were managed by owners themselves (Table no. 4). Majority of male ownership homestays are leased out completely with 75% whereas female ownership only 27%. It is because male are engaging in other activities and difficult to manage both whereas female prefers to manage their homestays with less number of room. Those female ownership homestay who have more rooms than half of them leased out because they find difficulties to manage in peak season as well as lack connection in tourist networks.

Table 5: Factors contributing to homestay leasing decisions among owners

Reason	Total	Percentage	Male (%)	Female (%)
To secure a steady income	20	83	15 (100)	9(100)
Lack of time to manage the homestay	24	100	15 (100)	5 (55)
Agents bring more tourists	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)
Total	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

Table no 5 represents the primary purpose for leasing their homestays to the external agents. All the owners of homestay reported that the external agents bring more tourists, indicating that owners recognize their value in attracting large clients. Agents likely have established networks and marketing platforms, which exacerbate the visibility and occupancy rates.

Table No.6: External agents involve homestay leasing

Organisation	Total	Percentage	Male	Female
Government Departments,	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Private Tour Operators.	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)
Local Community Groups,	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Total	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

The private tour operators are the sole external agents involved in the leasing of homestays in Sillery Gaon, accounting for 100% of the respondents (Table no 6).

Table no. 7: Role of agents in homestays and the regional development

Tourist method	Total	%	Male	Female
Infrastructure development (e.g., roads, electricity)	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Marketing and promotion of the destination	24	100	15(100)	9 (100)
Providing tourist for the homestays	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)
Total	24	100	15 (100)	7 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

Table no. 7 represents the different methods for the management of tourists by the homestay owners. The absence of the respondents in the infrastructural development signifies that the external agents have no such role in the improvement of physical infrastructure, such as roads and electricity. All owners both male and female agreed that the agents act as the tourists' providers in homestays, one of the most significant contributions for the local economy as well as marketing and promoting the destination and providing tourists for the homestays in Sillery Gaon.

Table No. 8: Distribution of homestay owners by positive impacts of leasing

Positive Impact	Total	%	Male	Female
Regular and predictable income	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)
Reduced management responsibilities for the owner	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)
Better marketing and promotion by agents	24	100	15 (100)	9 (100)
Higher-quality services for tourists	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Total	24	100	15(100)	9 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

All owners acknowledged benefit of leasing is regular and predictable income, reduces management responsibilities for the owners and better marketing and promotion of homestays by the agents (Table no 8). There are no respondents reported for the "higher quality services for tourists; this suggests that there may be skepticism about whether leasing actually improves the guest experience or a disconnect between management and service delivery.

Table No. 9 : Represents the contribution of homestay in the village

Contribution	Total	Percentage
Creating jobs	31	100
Solving unemployment problems in the village	27	87
Sourcing local goods and services	31	100
Promote organic farming and diversification of agriculture	31	100
Promoting local culture or crafts	31	100
Beautification of the village	31	100
Protection and increase concern of environment	31	100
Total	31	100

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

The contribution of homestay in the local economy in Sillery Gaon. All of them reported that homestays create jobs and somewhat solving unemployment problems of the village as a staff member, as taxi driver, good suppliers in the homestays. The employment generation during the tourist seasons reduce out migrations of youths especially women. It also reported that home enhances organic farming (fruits and vegetations) and promoting local culture or crafts among the visitors. All of them opined that homestays also concern about beautification and hygienic of surroundings and increasing protection of environment (Table no 9).

Local Resident (Non-Homestay Household)

Table no.10 Distribution of non homestay residents by occupation

Occupation	Total	Percentage	Male (%)	Female (%)
Farmer	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Owner of retails shop	5	83	1 (100)	4 (80)
Government Service	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Private Service	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)
Seasonal Worker (staff)	1	17	0 (0)	1 (20)
Total	6	100	1 (100)	5 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

Only male was found out of six households who did not have homestay and rest of the non homestay households were belonged to female with 83% and also 83% non homestay residents are doing small retails business, possibly due to relative low barrier for entry and easier compatibility with homestay operations (Table no 10). The mode of retails shop business might also enjoy flexibility for the operator to perform shopkeeping work while attending to other household activities mainly done by female. Only one non homestay resident is seasonal worker, who does homestay-related activities. She can afford to make more room for homestay. The sustained presence of seasonal worker adds some support to homestays, and create short-term employment in peak seasons.

Table No.11 Perceptions of Non homestay respondents towards Homestay

Perceptions	Total	Percentage
Increased cost of living	0	0
Environmental damage (e.g., littering, deforestation, water scarcity)	6	100
Cultural dilution or commercialization of traditions	6	50
Overcrowding and traffic congestion	6	100
Provide good income	6	100
Preservation of culture and protection of Environment	6	100
Total	6	100

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

The perceptions of non homestay residents in local community. Statistics indicate that none had considered a rise in living costs to be an issue. All the respondents agreed environmental damage, lack of appropriate waste management practices and excessive use of natural resources which negatively affect the environment but seasonal and at same time they also agreed that due to homestay there is constant concern of environment protection and progress in identifying their unique culture. They often feel a sense of pride in showcasing their culture and heritage. They all also agreed homestay bring good income for them. But all of them opined that there is cultural dilution due to commercialization of culture and heritage of the place. All residents reported that increased tourist traffic, noise, and a lack of parking and visitor management (Table no 11).

Staffs in The Homestays

There were 10 staffs engaged in homestays out of which 6 males and 4 females. The majority of them belong to 29–33 age group with 50% and 40% from 24-28. All together 90% of staffs belong to age group of 20-33 years. This suggests that young people are actively involved in hospitality. This is not a good sign with mere educational background. About 40% staffs have primary education, 30% have secondary education, 20% have graduation, and 10% have post-graduation. Out 10 staffs, 8 were local and 2 were from Siliguri. 7 staffs were male and 3 staffs were females.

Table No.12: Distribution of staffs by their role in homestays

Value	Roles	Total	Percentage	Male (%)	Female (%)
1	House Keeping	10	100	7 (100)	3(100)
2	Cooking	8	80	5 (71)	3 (100)
3	Guiding	7	70	7 (100)	0 (0)
4	Maintenance	10	70	7 (100)	3(100)
5	Receptionist	10	100	7 (100)	3(100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

The distribution of responsibilities among homestay staffs in Sillery Gaon. Housekeeping and maintenance works are done by all staffs both male and female. Only cooking and guiding where 71% of male and no female engage respectively (Table no 12). Most of staffs work more than 8 hours with 60% in a day and 40% staffs works between 4-8 hours. It is possible due to the nature of tourism-based services that call for long and unpredictable hours of work, such as cooking, cleaning, attaining to guest. According to the survey about 60% staffs have reported that the income is sufficient to meet their personal and family needs. This indicates a moderate level of income sufficiency, and that most workers are able to meet their basic needs. In contrast, 40% respondents reported for inadequate income. Among male staff about 57% reported that the income is sufficient for them, whereas, about 43% accounts for inadequacy. In contrast, about 67% female respondents found their income sufficient, and only 33% stated insufficiency of income. This data suggests that female staffs are sufficient with salary because their male partners also working. Non-monetary benefits like food, accommodation, and tips are also endorsed to all staffs.

Eco- Tourist

While conducting the survey, there were 15 domestic tourists in the homestays and no foreign tourists out of which 9 females and 6 males. The majority of the tourists with 67%, fall within the age group of 22-28, with 78% female and 50% of male visitors. This signifies that the Sillery Gaon is notably popular among the young people. A greater proportion of female tourists suggests that Sillery Gaon is seen as a secure and pleasant place for women, or they may choose rural and nature-oriented tourism.

Most of them were from Kolkata with 53% followed by Cooch Bihar and Malda with 30% and 20% respectively. There one eco tourist from Murshidabad (Table no 13).

Table No.13: Distribution of tourists based on their original place

Places	Total	Percentage	Male (%)	Female (%)
Cooch Behar	3	30	0 (0)	3 (33)
Kolkata	8	53	4 (67)	4 (45)
Malda	3	20	1 (17)	2 (22)
Murshidabad	1	7	1 (17)	0 (0)
Total	15	100	6 (100)	9 (100)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

Among them 27% were in government service with 33% of males and 22% females. Private service workers constitute 20 % of the respondents and all of them are women. This might suggest that a larger number of employed women are now traveling, which might be due to an increase in their independence and interest in short trips. The teachers and doctors accounts for about 20%. In term of visitation, 66% of the visitors for Sillery Gaon were visiting the place for the first time, which is a significant portion of the whole sample. This indicates that Sillery Gaon continues to attract new visitors.

Table No. 14: Purpose of visit of tourists in Sillery Gaon

Purpose	Total	Percentage	Male (%)	Female (%)
Relaxation	15	100	6 (100)	9 (100)
Adventure/Trekking	10	66	6 (100)	2 (22)
Cultural Exploration	10	66	2 (33)	4 (44)
Others	0	0	0 (0)	0 (0)

Source: Field Data (January-February, 2025)

The purpose of the tourists visiting to Sillery Gaon. All tourists' first priority of visiting were relaxation. Adventure and Cultural exploration were responded by 66% equally. Though all male tourists were coming for adventure and relaxation. Only 22% of women for adventure. This indicates that Sillery Gaon is considered as peaceful and calm destination with beautiful view of Mt Kanchenjunga, ideal for escaping from the stress of daily life. Maximum of tourists visit the village for one day with 67% and 33% tourists were for 2-3 days. They responded their excellent experience in the area with 67% and rest commented good. They found their favorite experience in scenic beauty, weather, view of the Mt Kanchenjunga (world's third highest peak) and 14 bends of Teesta, Bird watching, trekking etc (Table no 14).

Conclusion

The study of homestay tourism in Sillery Gaon presents a complex interaction of economy, culture, and environment. Stakeholders have reported mix opinions. Homestay tourism has become an alternative livelihood opportunity, appears to empower women and youth. It is connected to rural youth and strengthen the local economies. They also expose the community to new vulnerabilities. Reliance on the external agents, limited financial sources, and inadequate training have impacted the equitable distribution of economic benefits. Further, a shift towards modern constructions of household and prioritization of tourist preferences have results into the erosion of cultural purity in terms of traditional architecture, crafts and cultural practices. Environmentally, although the region retains significant ecological appeal, unregulated tourist inflows lead to weak waste management. It begins to strain local resources. Overall, the findings underscore the urgent need for capacity building, participatory planning, and policies that balance economic growth with

cultural preservation and ecological sustainability to secure homestay tourism as a resilient model of community development in Sillery Gaon.

Leasing of homestay has raised several issues. One common issue is that some agents falsely advertise, using photos of different or better-equipped homestays to entice tourists. This inaccurate portrayal results in unrealistic expectations and creates a misunderstanding between the landlord and the tourist. Additionally, many owners feel that agents prioritize their own profit over the actual quality and authenticity of the homestay experience. The efforts of local families, who manage every aspects of the service from fetching firewood for campfire, supply of organic vegetables, guiding tourist are often overlooked. The necessity of equitable profit-sharing mechanism and transparent communication are the key concern raised by homestay owners in order to maintain social cohesion within the community. The leasing of homestay processes should be based on mutual understanding, trust, and clarity among the agents about the facilities and limitations. However, leasing at the same time offers some relief to homestay owners through reduction on their work load, adoption of digital platforms and online booking tools encouraged to help homestay owners to become more independent and enhance direct engagement with tourists and constant income.

From a sustainability perspective, the region remains relatively attractive environmentally, but unregulated tourism, along with inadequate waste management, is affecting the local resources. Additionally, the findings highlight importance of strengthening locals and participatory plannings to develop ongoing policies that manage tensions which respond tourism development as incremental development, cultural and environmental sustainability to ensure sustainable homestay tourism (Das, 2023) as resilient model of community development in Sillery Gaon.

References

1. Acharya, B. P., & Halpenny, E. A. (2013). Homestays as an Alternative tourism product for Sustainable Community development: A case study of Women-Managed Tourism Product in Rural Nepal. *Tourism Planning & Development*, 10(4), 367–387. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568316.2013.779313>

2. Afua Afenyo-Agbe, E., University of Cape Coast, Mensah, I., & University of Cape Coast. (2022). Principles, Benefits, and Barriers to Community-Based Tourism: Implications for Management. In Chapter. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-7335-8.ch001>
3. Alamineh, G. A., Hussein, J. W., Mulu, Y. E., & Tadesse, B. (2023). The negative cultural impact of tourism and its implication on sustainable development in Amhara Regional State. *Cogent Arts and Humanities*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2023.2224597>
4. Census of India, 2011, Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India
5. Chapagai, P. P., Royal University of Bhutan, & Rai, B. M. (2018). Socio-Economic Impact of Homa-Stay Programm in Gangtey Valley. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371730745>
6. Das, B. (2024). Community-Based Tourism Approach for Sustainable Development: A study of the Lepcha Community, Kalimpong District, India. *Journal of Architectural/Planning Research and Studies (JARS)*, 21(2), 405–420. <https://doi.org/10.56261/jars.v21.264845>
7. District Statistical Office, Kalimpong. (2018). District statistical handbook: Kalimpong district. Bureau of Applied Economics and Statistics, Government of West Bengal.
8. Kumar, O. P. (2023). Community-based ecotourism in rural India: A case study of environmental conservation and economic empowerment. <https://ijeks.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/IJEKS2-11-012.pdf>
9. Maity, S. B., Sautya, J., & Sahoo, Dr. A. (2020). Changing pattern of houses and lifestyle of Sillery Gaon, Kalimpong, West Bengal. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention (IJHSSI)*, 9(1), 05–09. <https://www.ijhssi.org>
10. UNWTO. (2019). Tourism and the Sustainable Development Goals – Journey to 2030. United Nations World Tourism Organization. <https://www.eunwto.org/doi/book/10.18111/9789284419401>